

A THEORETICAL STUDY ON WOODEN TOY INDUSTRY-CASE STUDY OF SAWANTWADI, SINDHUDURGA DISTRICT, MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

The imported toys made by using modern technologies, plays over the conventional industries and affecting the smooth running of the craftsmanship. This Research article tries to depict the current scenario of wooden toy industry from Sawantwadi, Taluka from Sindhudurga District, Maharashtra. In India, many wooden toy makers give up their job like any other conventional profession due to lack of adequate earning and livelihood. These toy industries face a financial crisis for some year's results from changing trends and inadequate placing. Awareness of the benefits and value of eco-friendly toys are essential for the goodness of child development and boosting of the conventional industries.

Key words: Toys, Wooden, Craftsmen, Industry, Sawantwadi

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Introduction

It is nature that children look to when it comes to toys and playing. What touches one's heart is the simplicity of these toys that provide not just amusement to the child but also the means to learn while playing. When the child is born the rattle is the first choice to amuse with . It may be made fro bamboo, wood, cane and palm leaf. The wooden rattle is painted with bright colour to catch the attention of the child.

The abundant raw material present around the village is used to fashion harmless. These toys are biodegradable and made from environment friendly products. Old clthes and other fabrics are used to make stuffed toys and animals. Rajasthani stuffed toys are originated from these. India has a splendid tradition and history of wooden toys since 5000 years. Toys are known as

the timeless creation which guides children to adulthood. Wooden toy making is part of every state's art and culture in India, but only few place work is most famous and followed as traditional craft from centuries. Among such states Sawantwadi of Maharashtra is also known for its amazing work in wooden toys craft.

Sawantwadi is famous for its art and culture, popularly known for Ganjifa playing cards and wooden toys made from mango tree. The craft is traditionally done by the Chitari or Chitrakar community recognized by the king. These communities migrated from Karwada and settled in Sawantwadi. These families survived mainly by supplying handicrafts items to the royal families. Later other communities also adopted this craft because of its commercial success. Queen Satwasheela Devi continues the tradition even today, where many of the families are involved in Ganjifa cards and wooden toys making. The toys are made by assembling flat shaped solid wood. Seasoned mango wood is chiseled or carved into desired toy shape. The cutout pieces are finished on a sander, painted and assembled.

Observations from Review of Literature

Indian Toys Market Drivers

- Driven by a huge consumer base, India represents an important market for toys. With a population of around 1.3 Billion, it is the second largest populated country in the world. Moreover, the country has a very large young population with around half of the total population under the age of 25.
- The increasing domestic demand for toys in India is also being catalysed by the country's strong economic growth and rising disposable incomes. India has exhibited strong GDP growth rates for the last several years and now represents amongst the world's largest economies. Driven by this trend, the middle-class population has experienced strong growth in the region. consumers have more disposable incomes and their spending patterns have also changed. This has resulted in a major shift from traditional, medium- to low-end battery-operated toys, towards innovative electronic toys, intelligent toys as well as upmarket plush toys.
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Objectives of the Study

1. To study and understand the cultural identity of the craft Sawantwadi
2. To study the transition of the craft from historical importance to the commercial product.
3. To understand the current scenario of the craft.
4. To evolve future strategies for growth and development of the craft Sawantwadi.

Hypothesis of Study

Sawantwadi wooden toy handicrafts industry is contributing towards an important source of income of the small artisans in the Konkan region.

Research Methodology

The study is based on Primary and Secondary data.

For primary data collection Observation method of data collection is used.

For Secondary data Magazines, Journals, Research Papers are considered.

Making of wooden toys Tools and Raw Materials

Basic raw material used to make Sawantwadi wooden toys is Mango wood and Sivani wood. The raw material is purchased locally and sent to the saw mill for sizing wood blocks and planks. The wood is cut and processed into desired shape using following tools and machines- **Thin Blade saw-** is used to cut the wood into required or desired shape.

Turning machine- the wood piece is fixed to the turning machine and chiseled into required toy shape.

Chisel- different types of chisel such as flat, curve and pointed chisels are used to carve the wood to the desired shape of toy.

Sander- a turning machine fixed with a sanding belt used for sanding process. The rough edges of the wood pieces are smoothed using this machine.

The coloring process is done using oil based colors. Various shades of colour powder is mixed with wood primer and applied on the toy using brush. Craftsmen also use spray guns to spray paint to finish the work faster. Thin paint brush is used in the end to add details and outlines on the toys.

The parts of the toys are assembled using nails and hammer. Other accessories like plastic wheels, chains, threads and buttons are also fixed in the end.

Findings of Study

It is covered in the form of SWOT analysis

Strengths

1. Products are light weight. So it is easy to carry.
2. The wood required to produce the toys is available in the surrounding area.
3. Specialty in wooden fruit making which resembles like actual one.
4. Sustainable products. Less chances of breakage
5. Product is not perishable and lasts for many years.
6. More demand during the festival seasons.
7. High quality skill set.

Weaknesses

1. Quality Issue: It was found that there are holes in the wood which needs to be removed before colouring the product, but the artisans are unskilled and they lack this skill which leads to visibility of holes after some period.
2. Seasonal Market: Most of the sale happens during festival where fruits are used for decoration. Except this period the market has less number of customers.
3. Threat for products from other regions: The products face direct competition from States like Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu as well as from countries like China which attract the customers due to low prices and variety.
4. Lack of marketing and promotion: The local artisans lack the promotion skills. They are far away from the strategies like Marketing mix, Brand Building, Integrated Marketing Communication.

5. Use of Technology: The machines and equipment which are used by artisans are old and outdated . It is necessary to introduce the sophisticated techniques of production.

Opportunities

1. The toys market has huge potential specifically toys used in education. Many schools use toys to help children to understand concept in detail. A tie up with schools will ensure constant order to manufacturers;
2. There is a huge sales potential in the export market.
3. Formation of clusters will help to raise the potential demand.
4. Luxury sector is an untapped market.
5. E-Commerce can help
6. Collaborations with designers or brands
7. Sale in small Government or Cooperatives
8. Can apply for GI

Threats/ Challenges

1. Regulation on the tree cutting can lead to increase in prices of wood.
2. More import from Chinese toys will be real threat to domestic market, There is a stiff competition from plastic toys manufacturers which are comparatively cheaper.
3. The new generation is moving away from craft and the traditional fruit making art is on the verge of dying.
4. People are buying physical toys less in lieu of digital India.

Suggestions of Study

1. Forming a cluster: Increase the competitiveness of the cluster by integrated use of design and technology to design products aimed at meeting the needs of the market based on digital economy and globalisation for encouraging economic growth.
2. Creating categories and innovative products with design and research in mind
3. Developing of Enterprise network and business linkages as under:
 - Creating demand
 - IPR protection Packaging
 - Crafts Tourism
 - Corporate Tie ups
 - Visit to fairs ad exhibitions (National and International)

- Creation of catalogue for marketing products
- E-Commerce & Website development
- Conclusion

4. Safety and Environment Responsibility

The craft needs to put under strict quality standards and regular quality checks should be maintained which will lead to thrust building among the customers.

Safety: The toys should be manufactured in compliance with all current international safety standards.

5. Working conditions:

The cluster should focus and offer human working conditions in the cluster members in their own production plants. The cluster should deal with their employees in a correct and proper manner and offer them safety and healthy working environment.

6. Export market: Complying to International standards. It is necessary to adopt international needs and colour preferences.

Conclusion

Globalisation has brought tremendous changes in the pattern of purchase, consumption, consumer choices etc. Though Sawantwadi toy industry has contributed as steady source of income of the artisans, preserved the art of Konkan region, satisfied the need of consumers since last many years, now it is facing a tough competition from internal and external competitors, big business houses and MNCs. To survive and succeed in future it is necessary to focus on the handicraft industry in general and Sawantwadi toy industry in particular.

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